

WOMEN, PEACE AND SECURITY AGENDA: PERSPECTIVES FOR BRAZIL

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ABSTRACT

In the 2000s, the UN Security Council signed Resolution 1325 on Women, Peace and Security. In a context of resignification of conflicts, on new approaches to security and peace, academics and new researchers have focused on the role of women as victims and agents in the war environment, thus emerging new studies on the female role in the pacification process of conflicts.

The MPS Agenda, Women, Peace and Security, has the primary objective of encouraging UN signatory countries to expand female participation in decision-making processes on national and international agendas, expressing gender equality as a key factor in international security issues and peacebuilding. Therefore, the objective of this policy brief is to address the policies directed by the UN and those implemented in Brazil so that the MPS Agenda materializes with the equal participation of women in peacekeeping missions, since the participation of Brazilian civilians and military fit this profile of promoting and building peace.

BACKGROUND

More than 20 years ago, the United Nations Security Council implemented the Agenda on Women, Peace and Security through resolution 1325ⁱⁱⁱ. Over these years, to consolidate the gender equity proposal, nine other resolutions were signed, promoting public policies in the signatory countries to achieve a considerable number of female participation at strategic and operational levels. Currently, we can consider that the UN managed to mobilize and articulate policies in favor of this agenda, one of which was promoted and disseminated through UN Women.

UN Women is dedicated to gender equality and women's empowerment by helping countries implement policies, laws, programs and services that can benefit women and girls around the world. To achieve this goal, UN Women has been working with some efforts aimed at women's leadership on an equal basis in governance systems; the search for work with income security and economic autonomy; the fight against all forms of violence against women and female participation in conflict resolution and in the search for peaceful relations in the world. These strategic points outline programs and guide countries in institutionalizing policies that promote equal protection for women.

In the debate on gender equality as a basic human right, UN Women implemented a UN Women Strategic Plan 2022-2025 with a view to also achieving the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, including noting aspects of the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action^{iv}. With the challenges in the international context for the insertion, integration and effective participation of women in global development activities, UN Women decided to address and implement policies, as well as seek results, observing four main focuses: governance and female participation in public life, women's economic empowerment, ending violence against women and girls, and promoting the Women, Peace and Security agenda in humanitarian action and in disaster situations. This last approach by UN Women, which we will continue to discuss, is the focus of this work on the discussion of the participation of military and civilian women in conflict zones, thus returning to the analysis of resolution 1325 from a historical perspective.

Over these 23 years of the MPS Agenda, 9 resolutions were signed, highlighting the consolidation of the proposal for gender equality and female participation in building and maintaining peace, humanitarian response and post-conflict reconstruction. To ensure collaboration and coordination of efforts in implementing the gender equality agenda through resolution 1325, the Interagency Network on Women and Gender Equality established the Task Force on Women, Peace and Security with the aim of carrying out joint responses in the United Nations system and its member countries to achieve the resolution's priorities, as well as a critical analysis of the implementation of the Beijing Platform for Action on Women in Armed Conflict.^v

Task Force on Women, Peace and Security was initiated in 2004 to guarantee and strengthen resolution 1325, incorporate the work agenda, encourage partnerships, coordinate activities, monitor activities to insert women in the international security agenda, improve policies and monitor the positive indicators that meet this agenda. The Task Force's composition had 20 members and 5 NGO observers and carried out an important work to subsidize information and decision-making by the UN Secretary General based on his working group.

In 2002 the Security Council requested the full implementation of resolution 1325. In 2003, the Task Force developed an action plan with recommendations to be implemented and in 2004 concluded with an informative and indicative report about the actions for the consolidation of the Women, Peace and Security agenda. The report focused on developing an action plan strategy for incorporating gender perspectives in conflict prevention and resolution; integrate gender perspectives into peacekeeping activities; incorporate gender perspectives into all thematic reports.

With the recommendations of the Security Council and the construction of a positive agenda around the participation of women in peace and security actions, the signatories of resolution 1325 began adapting and implementing policies to increase women's participation in this action. Thus, they began the construction of the National Action Plans (NAPs) on Women, Peace and Security as one of the results.

RESULTS

Currently, 105 members of the United Nations have adopted Resolution 1325. Of these, approximately 54 countries have adopted 1 National Action Plan on Women, Peace and Security, 27 countries have adopted 2 plans, 17 countries have developed 3 plans and 6 countries are already in their fourth version. According to PeaceWomen^{vi} 33% of plans are out of date. Brazil, for example, adopted its first plan in 2017, being valid between 2017 and 2019, since then it remains outdated. On the other hand, countries like Portugal, Holland, Denmark are already in the fourth version of the document, or even Australia and adopted a last version for 10 years (2021-2031), with continuous policies of implementation of the MPS agenda. Below is a table for analysis of the 105 countries that adopted the National Action Plan and the respective years of their first effective plans.

Source: <http://1325naps.peacewomen.org>

For Brazil, the National Action Plan on Women, Peace and Security was adopted in 2017, following a series of policies adopted to encourage the participation of women in the international security agenda. Some of these policies expanded or enabled female participation in training and career

schools in the armed forces so that women could quantitatively have greater representation in the military sphere.

In order to understand the historical aspect of the participation of Brazilian women in the Armed Forces, the first women acted in the Second World War when they had auxiliary participation as caregivers or nurses in the conflict, but this did not characterize a female career in the Armed Forces. Only in 1980, the Brazilian Navy authorized the entry of women in the institution and, in 1982, the Brazilian Air Force would follow the same path by creating the Female Staff of Officers and the Female Staff of Graduates. It was only after 10 years, in 1992, that the Brazilian Army included women in the Complementary Staff of Officers.

The late career for women and always linked to the administrative body of military institutions made it difficult for women to enter international missions, since they acted as observers or in the General Staff, however, they hardly entered the troop to act in the conflict. In 1996, the Air Force began admitting women to the management staff at the Air Force Academy and, in 2003, it was able to enroll in the Training Course for Aviator Officers.

However, it was in 2012, with Law nº 12.705^{vii}, signed by President Dilma Rousseff, which the requirements for entering the career military training course, authorized the entry of women into the military line, signaling to the Brazilian Army that they would have 5 years to enable the entry of female candidates in admission contests the Military Academy. Even so, barriers continue to exist for the empowerment of military women, such as: only 10% of vacancies are reserved for women in military academies; they cannot choose base specialties (Infantry and Cavalry) or support specialties (Artillery, Communications and Engineering), only Quartermaster Service and Ordnance Corps; moreover, the condition of soldiers cannot be voluntary as a military service.

Another advance was the creation of the Gender Commission of the Ministry of Defense (CGMD) with Ordinance No. 893 of April 14, 2014^{viii}. This commission had an advisory nature, at a strategic level and directly linked to the Minister's Office. Its main objectives were to articulate policies, carry out reports and carry out actions for women's rights and gender equality. In 2019, Ordinance 3695/GM-MD revoked Ordinance No. 893 and ended the Gender Commission of the Ministry of Defense, leading the gender debate within the Ministry of Defense to a new setback.

A survey carried out by the Igarapé Institute brought some relevant data as a result of investigations on Brazilian women in peacekeeping missions and thus numerically analyze the female representation. According to the researchers, between 1992 and 2019 Brazilian women (military, police and civilians) participated in 25 UN peacekeeping missions, out of a universe of 48,163 Brazilians. This means 0.7% of the total amount. We can observe with this research a still very small number of female participation and without comparative data to previous periods, since the UN did not carry out this type of registration or cadastre.

Some challenges highlighted by the researchers should be mentioned as a reflection of the low rate of women in peacekeeping missions, including social expectations about the role of women with a focus on caregiving, which means that these women are hardly able to be absent from their socially imposed functions; the proportionately smaller number of women in the Armed Forces or career civilians in the Ministry of Defense also reflects the low number of women in missions; low participation at higher hierarchical levels, for example, Brazil has only 4 women at general level; little disclosure and information about the selection processes; inherent risks and sacrifices for women and the need for pre-mission preparation and training.

Thus, the Igarapé Institute report lists situations that require critical analysis and rapid correction so that women can be included and participate effectively in security actions and the promotion of international peace, whether at the highest levels of politics or strategy, or even, at operational and tactical levels, offering protection to other women victims of the scourges of war.

CONCLUSIONS

After 23 years of policies for the implementation of UN Resolution 1325 and a series of recommendations from the organization for the female insertion in matters of security and peace, we observe a discontinuity of the process in Brazil. Advances were made by laws and maintained by institutions. However, government agendas and party priorities did not allow for significant advances and dismantled the necessary bridges to expand the agenda of women in peacekeeping missions.

Currently, discourses on meritocracy or discourses that express the inability of women in the operational field, that is, as troops, have been politically polarized and make civil society unable to perceive the real role of women as promoters of peace, conflict resolution and the peaceful sustainability of international relations.

In 2018, the UN created the Uniformed Gender Parity Strategy ^{ix} defining new goals by 2028. Among these more realistic goals are those of increasing the number of military women as observers and belonging to the staff of General Staff officers by more than 25% and women members of military troops by more than 15%. However, in order to meet this perspective, it is necessary for Brazil to once again reformulate the effective entry of women into the military career in its military institutions and strive so that they can remain and continue to participate in peacekeeping missions.

These are some relevant points for Brazil's role in the international context and its effective participation in multilateral forums such as the UN. Compliance with the organization's recommendations offers a positive reputation, greater reliability to partners, continuous construction in processes for the pursuit of international peace and security. In the meantime, the participation of women and the construction,

application and recognition of affirmative gender policies become necessary for our peacekeepers and for the Brazilian Foreign Policy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

As a way of expanding the critical debate, studies and analysis of gender policies in the Brazilian Armed Forces, as well as in the Ministry of Defense, in order to considerably achieve a more effective participation of military and civilian women in Defense and in peacekeeping missions, we recommend:

- 1- The Gender Commission of the Ministry of Defense be restructured and activated with the objective of coordinating efforts with the armed forces in the creation of policies for the inclusion and participation of women in the military career, rethinking the entry of women into military academies, the entry of women in the civil defense career and their participation in conflict resolution and stability actions for peace.
- 2- Update of the National Action Plan on Women, Peace and Security
- 3- Implement and monitor institutional policies applied to the benefit of women's insertion and participation of women in international activities.
- 4- Build an informative database for comparative use in the evaluation and monitoring of indicators.
- 5- Expand information about the selection process for women in peace missions and humanitarian actions.
- 6- Guarantee transparency in the selection process, in the information offered and in the curricular indications.
- 7- Promote and improve the training and qualification of women volunteers for the work of peacekeepers, encouraging that their training is not carried out only on demand, but that since their entry into the force, women volunteers can be mapped to peace missions so that training can be carried out, training and capacity building more adequately, for a longer time and in a continuous and consistent way;
- 8- Furthermore, promote a political debate that can guarantee the regulation and implementation of norms for gender equality.

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